

A STUDY ON THE EVALUATION OF THE SUITABILITY OF SUSTAINABLE TOURISM AND RECREATION TYPES IN RURAL COASTAL AREAS IN THE WESTERN BLACK SEA REGION

BATI KARADENİZ BÖLGESİ'NDE KIRSAL KIYI ALANLARINDA SÜRDÜRÜLEBİLİR TURİZM VE REKREASYON TİPLERİNİN UYGUNLUĞUNUN DEĞERLENDİRİLMESİ ÜZERİNE BİR ÇALIŞMA

Kübra TEKAMAR^a Canan CENGİZ^b

Abstract

Increasing mobility and trends to enhance the tourism experience are important factors in the growth of tourism. Today, tourism is becoming the world's largest industry with both direct and indirect socio-economic impacts. Rural coastal areas offer a unique combination of tourism with the beauties of nature and the richness of local culture. Rural coastal areas are places with high touristic potential as they are home to communities that preserve their natural beauty, traditional lifestyles and local cultural heritage, but this potential needs to be assessed and managed in a sustainable manner. Protecting natural resources and the environment, controlling the intensity of tourism activities and ensuring environmental sustainability are critical factors for the long-term success of tourism in rural coastal areas. In tourism planning, it is very important to identify suitable locations in order to establish future tourism infrastructures. The aim of this study is to analyse the natural and cultural landscape features of Kızılkum village and its immediate surroundings in Bartın province, located in the Western Black Sea Region, and to evaluate them in terms of sustainable tourism and recreation potential within the framework of conservation and utilisation principles. In this context, tourism and recreation activities that may be suitable for the study area were determined in line with expert opinions, and suitable area(s) were determined by considering the evaluation criteria in line with the data obtained for eight proposed tourism and recreation activities.

Keywords: Sustainability, Tourism and Recreation, Rural Coastal, Bartın

Özet

Artan hareketlilik ve turizm deneyimini artırma eğilimleri, turizmin büyümesindeki önemli faktörlerdendir. Turizm günümüzde hem doğrudan hem de dolaylı olarak sosyo-ekonomik etkileri ile dünyanın en büyük endüstrisi haline gelmektedir. Kırsal kıyı alanları, doğanın güzellikleri ve yerel kültürün zenginlikleri ile turizmin özgün bir bileşimini sunmaktadır. Kırsal kıyı alanları, doğal güzellikleri, geleneksel yaşam tarzları ve yerel kültürel mirası koruyan topluluklara ev sahipliği yapmasıyla turistik potansiyeli yüksek yerlerdir, ancak bu potansiyelin sürdürülebilir bir şekilde değerlendirilmesi ve yönetilmesi gerekmektedir. Doğal kaynakların ve çevrenin korunması, turizm faaliyetlerinin yoğunluğunun kontrol edilmesi ve çevresel sürdürülebilirliğin sağlanması, kırsal kıyı bölgelerinde turizmin uzun vadeli başarısı için kritik öneme sahip faktörlerdir. Gelecekteki turizm altyapılarını kurmak amacıyla turizm planlamalarında, uygun yerlerin tanımlanması oldukça önem arz etmektedir. Bu çalışmanın amacı, Batı Karadeniz Bölgesinde yer alan Bartın ili Kızılkum köyü ve yakın çevresine yönelik doğal ve kültürel peyzaj özelliklerinin incelenerek, koruma kullanım ilkeleri çerçevesinde, sürdürülebilir turizm ve rekreasyon potansiyeli açısından değerlendirilmesidir. Bu kapsamda, çalışma alanı için uygun olabilecek turizm ve rekreasyon aktiviteleri uzman görüşleri doğrultusunda belirlenmiş olup, önerilen sekiz turizm ve rekreasyon aktiviteleri için elde edilen veriler doğrultusunda değerlendirme kriterleri göz önünde bulundurularak uygun alan/alanlar tespit edilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sürdürülebilirlik, Turizm ve Rekreasyon, Kırsal Kıyı, Bartın

Article Submission Date: 02.02.2024 Article Acceptance Date: 25.03.2024

Corresponding Author: Kübra TEKAMAR (kubraozturk94@gmail.com)

* This article is derived from the master's thesis titled "Evaluation of Coastal Landscapes in Terms of Sustainable Tourism and Recreation Potential: Bartın-Kızılkum Case" completed under the supervision of Prof. Dr. Canan CENGİZ at Bartın University Graduate School of Natural and Applied Sciences in 2018.

^a Bartın University, Postgraduate Education Institute, Bartın/Türkiye (kubraozturk94@gmail.com), ORCID: 0000-0002-2952-6298

^b Bartın University, Faculty of Engineering, Bartın/Türkiye (canancengiz@bartin.edu.tr), ORCID: 0000-0003-1492-1081

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10895912

1. Introduction

Tourism is increasingly becoming important for sustainable economic and social development in rural and remote communities worldwide (Stoddart et al., 2020). According to data from the World Tourism Organization (WTO), tourism stands as the globe's most significant sector in terms of both participant volume and its consequential economic influence (Miller et al., 2002). Tourism is one of the fastest-growing economic activities worldwide. It offers significant advantages in terms of creating employment and enhancing the quality of life for the regions in which it is established. However, unplanned tourism growth is also associated with disadvantages due to the negative impacts caused by the degradation and fragmentation of the natural, social and economic environment (Aguilar-Becerra et al., 2017). Within the tourist carrying capacity of each region, tourism should not only emphasise local culture and productive economy (Castellani and Sallas, 2009) but also trigger local development (Lantitsou, 2017).

Tourism necessitates sustainable planning methodologies that facilitate destinations in upholding robust economies while concurrently safeguarding environmental and cultural integrity (Aguilar-Becerra et al., 2017). According to Latip et al. (2015), the basis of sustainable tourism development is based on three important pillars: environmental, economic and socio-cultural (Susila et al., 2023). Sustainable tourism is widely recognized internationally in policy decisions and scientific studies as a way to preserve the natural environment and traditional and cultural heritage, while also enhancing local development (Castellani and Sallas, 2009). The endeavor towards sustainable tourism is exemplified by the judicious utilization of environmental assets, thereby securing enduring sustainability through the equitable distribution of socio-economic advantages to all stakeholders, particularly emphasizing local communities, alongside the preservation and enhancement of tourist satisfaction (Susila et al., 2023).

Establishing environmentally sustainable tourism hinges on establishing socially sustainable tourism networks that facilitate host communities in reaping benefits from tourism development (Stoddart et al., 2020). According to Nelson (1994), community access to the management and development of resources is an significant aspect of sustainable tourism (Susila et al., 2023). Studies conducted in rural, coastal, and island communities demonstrate that the effective execution of sustainable tourism initiatives is contingent upon the involvement and contributions of local stakeholders (Stoddart et al., 2020).

Tourism is considered one of the key sectors that can contribute to the enhancement and sustainability of quality of life in rural areas (Utami et al., 2023). Rural tourism encompasses

any tourism modality that highlights rural life, arts, culture, and heritage, facilitating engagement between tourists and local inhabitants to yield economic and social advantages for the community while enhancing the tourism encounter (Aref and Gill, 2009). Scenic areas comprising diverse ecosystems possess significant potential to stimulate tourism growth in rural regions and serve as essential components of rural tourism (Ayhan, et al., 2020).

Rural tourism is an activity that takes place mainly in the rural areas (Aref and Gill, 2009). The development of modern rural tourism requires an in-depth study of the characteristic rural culture and a continuous enhancement of the tourism attractiveness of rural areas (Fan, 2020).

Rural tourism has long been recognized as a way to achieve economic and social development and regeneration (Sharpley, 2002). Rural tourism is recognized as a valid development strategy for rural areas in many developed and developing countries (Ayhan, et al., 2020). Negrusa et al. (2007) defines rural tourism as a form of tourism implied by small-scale accommodations and rural activities, along with the traditions of life, in rural areas by people (Aref and Gill, 2009). Rural coastal regions are regions with significant potential for tourism due to their natural beauties and traditional lifestyles. The emergence of coastal tourism as a scholarly subject is asserted to be "wholly secured by present-day global circumstances," owing to the substantial expansion of tourism as a worldwide phenomenon during the latter part of the twentieth century (Rogerson and Rogerson, 2020). Coastal tourism entails the interaction between tourists and the destinations they visit, with particular emphasis on the coastal environment and its natural as well as cultural assets (Miller et al., 2002). Coastal regions have been historically acknowledged as immensely valuable locales for leisure activities, with the trend of traveling to coastal areas for recreational purposes being a ubiquitous phenomenon throughout human civilization (Rogerson and Rogerson, 2020). Coastal tourism destinations are situated within an urban-rural continuum. Numerous coastal tourism destinations provide visitors with diverse combinations of cultural, historical, social, environmental, and additional intrinsic values (Miller et al., 2002). The maritime tourism sector has been developed to increase economic growth, construct alternative tourism, enhance people's well-being, eradicate poverty, and overcome unemployment (Fithor, et al., 2020). In fact, many coastal tourism activities are considered a job for those in the tourism sector and an experience for tourists (Miller et al., 2002). Nowadays, coastal tourism studies can no longer be equated solely with sun, sea, and sand (3S) leisure tourism (Rogerson and Rogerson, 2020).

The emerging sector of rural tourism, which integrates agriculture and tourism, is garnering growing attention from society at large (Li, 2020). Agritourism is evolving as a means of diversifying agricultural activities in rural communities and as an alternative agricultural pursuit

capable of bolstering agricultural sustainability. This entails broadening the economic foundation, offering training avenues for agritourists, enhancing environmental stewardship, fostering local cultural heritage and traditions, and fostering increased community cohesion (Tawfik and Elsebaei, 2022). Given the diversification of consumer preferences and enhancements in quality of life, it becomes imperative to reevaluate and thoroughly understand the ecology, structure, and cultural dynamics inherent in rural regions. Subsequently, it is crucial to augment the quality of rural tourism products and foster innovation grounded in this framework (Li, 2020).

Sumantra et al. (2017) suggest that the development of agro-tourism can be achieved through identifying competitive advantages based on distinctive features, whether they arise from unique local flora or fauna; producing value-added products from regional resources to enhance the value chain; strengthening regional cultural diversity; and promoting captivating natural landscapes and local wildlife (Susila et al., 2023).

Agrotourism presents novel opportunities for fostering sustainable development in rural areas, providing urban residents with authentic rural experiences, and presenting farmers and landowners with viable economic alternatives. It encompasses both economic and non-economic advantages (Tawfik and Elsebaei, 2022). Sustainable development is defined as meeting the needs of the present while preserving the capacity of future generations to meet their own needs (Susila et al., 2023).

Agrotourism is not a new phenomenon; however, it has increased significantly at the beginning of the current century and is expected to increase further in the future. A form of rural tourism, agro-tourism not only creates new sources of income for local businesses but also provides an opportunity for local residents to participate in the preservation of indigenous resources and culture. Agritourism is associated with various terms used to refer to similar agricultural activities, such as rural tourism, agricultural tourism, agrotourism and agritainment (Tawfik and Elsebaei, 2022; Susila et al., 2023).

Agrotourism is an innovative strategy with great capacity to generate additional income, provide employment opportunities, maintain the integrity of the rural area, bridge the gap between rural and urban citizens, strengthen community cohesion, sustain social welfare, promote culture and the environment and ensure sustainability (Tawfik and Elsebaei, 2022). The success of sustainable agrotourism depends on the willingness of the community to respond to consumer demand with innovative approaches, while at the same time recognising the importance of sustainable business practices and overcoming what Winter (2003) calls “defensive localism” (Susila et al., 2023).

Consequently, achieving sustainability necessitates a thorough examination of these factors in crafting an agrotourism management plan to mitigate environmental degradation and prevent unwarranted exploitation of the local community's culture (Susila et al., 2023).

1.1. Land Suitability Assessment

Land evaluation involves analyzing land attributes to determine its appropriateness for various land use or crop types (Mazahreh et al., 2019). Site suitability is a process that explores the benefits of potential areas where a particular use or action could be realized (Jayaraman et al., 2021).

Suitability analyses involve the utilization of a wide range of methods from various scientific disciplines, and the outcomes are utilized across all domains of sustainable development. Suitability analyses constitute a process for determining the suitability and appropriateness of a specific area for a particular use, as well as the degree of suitability (Ayhan et al., 2020). An innovative methodology has been devised for land suitability mapping, which integrates soil and climate data tailored specifically for land suitability evaluation purposes (Mazahreh, et al., 2019).

The fundamental approach to land suitability assessment entails aligning the land's characteristics or attributes with the soil requirements of various land use categories. This process essentially entails delineating the climatic, soil, and land characteristics needed for the specified land use type. The site suitability method involves identifying observable indications of suitable areas for a particular land use activity, taking into account physical factors (such as elevation, slope, aspect, and climate), natural factors (including soil, topography, hydrology, vegetation cover, and ecologically sensitive areas), as well as existing land use and infrastructure (such as transportation networks, established urban areas, and utility systems) (Mazahreh, et al., 2019; Jayaraman et al., 2021).

Today, Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are recognised as a valuable decision support system that enables the determination of suitable spatial locations for a specific purpose based on a set of criteria (Jayaraman et al., 2021). GIS and remote sensing technologies are extensively employed to assess site suitability and conduct resource inventories based on environmental, socio-economic, and spatial planning considerations (Šiljeg et al., 2019).

A critical aspect of land suitability assessment involves establishing threshold values (criteria), typically defined by researchers relying on prior investigations and expertise (Mazahreh et al., 2019). GIS applications have the potential to augment the effectiveness of regulations within the travel industry. GIS can be regarded as a versatile toolkit comprising various methodologies and advancements suitable for fostering economic advancements in the travel sector

(Jayaraman et al., 2021).

The aim of this study is to determine and evaluate the tourism and recreation potential of Kızılkum Village, which stands out with its natural and cultural landscape features, and to develop area-specific recommendations in this direction. In this context, tourism and recreation activities suitable for the study area were determined based on expert opinions regarding Kızılkum Village and its immediate surroundings. In addition, natural and cultural landscape features in the study area were determined and recommendations were developed based on the principle of protecting and utilising resource values for tourism and recreational purposes.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

The administrative boundaries of Büyükkızılkum, Hatipler and Küçükkızılkum villages of Bartın province located in the Western Black Sea Region were accepted as the study area boundary. It is the widest and longest sandy beach of the province with highly productive ecological areas and coastal formations. The study area is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Study Area

Natural and cultural landscape features of the research area were determined and analyses were made on topography (elevation, slope and aspect), geological structure, soil structure (major soil groups, land use capability classes and erosion status), hydrological structure, vegetation cover (stand type, forest management class, forest closure), transportation status and current land use.

2.2. Expert Opinion Evaluation for the Determination of Tourism Types

A questionnaire was applied to 25 experts in order to determine the priority tourism activities suitable for the research area. For expert opinion, 25 experts from various professional disciplines such as architects, urban planners, forest engineers, tourism, mining technicians, mapping engineers, civil engineers, mining engineers, journalists, including 11 landscape architects, were consulted. The experts' selection relied on the work of Cengiz et al (2022). In the questionnaire, in which the natural and cultural characteristics of the area were taken into consideration, the experts were asked to prioritize the activities they thought to be prioritized for the area among 21 tourism activities by scoring them from 1 to 5 (1: not suitable 2: less suitable 3: moderately suitable 4: moderately suitable 5: very suitable). According to the survey results, both "scenic viewing and nature photography" activity and "swimming" activity received the highest score of 4.44, indicating that they are "highly suitable" for the area. The experts determined that "tent camping" activity with a score of 4.16, followed by "caravan camping" and "boat trips" activities with scores of 4.12 each, are "suitable" for the area. However, "land hunting" activity received the lowest score (2.76), indicating that its suitability is "slightly suitable" for the area.

2.3. The Identified Tourism and Recreation Activities

Considering the evaluation of natural and cultural features and taking into account expert opinions, in addition to tourism activities such as scenic viewing and nature photography, tent camping, caravan camping, trekking, picnicking, swimming, and boat trips directed towards Kızılkum, suitable areas have been identified for eight tourism activities, including agritourism, proposed as a tourism type for the study area.

The evaluation criteria for land suitability assessment were determined based on previous scientific studies. For identifying suitable areas for trekking, criteria from Sözen and Şahin (1988), Anonim (1996), Topay (2003) and Benliay (2009) were utilized. Evaluation criteria for tent camping activity were drawn from Ergör (1984), Havur (2002), Topay (2003) and Benliay (2009). Picnic areas were assessed based on criteria from Topay (2003) and Benliay (2009). Criteria for agritourism were sourced from Okyar et al. (1991), Doğaner (1996), Kiper (2006) and Giran Taşçıoğlu (2016). The evaluation criteria of tourism types are presented in Table 1. The flow chart of the study is given in Figure 2.

Table 1: Evaluation Criteria for Tourism Types

Evaluation Criteria		Most Suitable	Suitable
Trekking	Slope %	0-20	20-45
	Aspect	Flat, E, N, W, NE, NW	S, SE, SW
	Altitude (m)	0-326	-

	Landslide situation (slope %)	0-10	-
	Geological and geomorphological structure	Exist	-
	Proximity to water sources (m)	0-300	300-600
	Land capability classes	I, II, III, IV, VI, VII, coast	
	Current land use	Forest, heathland, fallow-free dry farming, coastal dunes	-
	Presence of natural plants	All types of vegetation	-
	Relative humidity	30-80	-
	Average wind speed (m/s)	0-10	10-15
	Proximity to accommodation and shelter facilities	0-3000	3000 +
	Presence of existing pathways	Exist	-
	Transport distance (m)	0-3000	3000 +
Tent Camping	Slope %	0-15	-
	Aspect	Flat, E, S, SE, SW, W	N, NE, NW
	Altitude (m)	0-326	-
	Landslide situation (slope %)	0-30	-
	Proximity to water sources (m)	0-250	250-500
	Land capability classes	IV, VI, VII, coast	-
	Current land use	Forest, heathland, fallow-free dry farming, coastal dunes	-
	Presence of natural plants	Leafy forest, mixed forest, treeless area	Coniferous forest
	Forest cover (%)	0-70	-
	Relative humidity	30-80	-
	Average wind speed (m/s)	0-10	10-15
	Presence of flood area	None	-
	Transport distance (m)	0-3000	3000 +
Caravan Camping	Slope %	0-15	-
	Aspect	Flat, E, S, SE, SW, W	N, NE, NW
	Altitude (m)	0-326	-
	Landslide situation (slope %)	0-30	-
	Proximity to water sources (m)	50 +	-
	Current land use	Forest, heathland, Fallow-free dry farming, coastal dunes	-
	Presence of natural plants	Open and semi-open areas	-
	Forest cover (%)	0-40	-
	Relative humidity	30-80	-
	Average wind speed (m/s)	0-10	10-15
	Presence of flood area	None	-
Transport distance (m)	0-100	-	
Picnic	Slope %	0-10	-
	Aspect	Flat, E, S, SE, SW, W	-
	Altitude (m)	5-200	200 +
	Landslide situation (slope %)	0-30	-
	Proximity to water sources (m)	0-250	250-500
	Land capability classes	IV, V	VII
	Current land use	Rangeland, meadow, forest, heathland	-
	Presence of natural plants	Leafy forest, mixed forest, semi-open areas	-
	Forest cover	0-70	-
Transport distance (m)	0-500	500 +	

(Table 1 continues)

	Evaluation Criteria	Most Suitable	Suitable
Scenic view./Nature pho.	Landslide situation (slope %)	45	-
	Peaks (m)	50	-
	Proximity to water sources (m)	500-1000	1000 +
	Current land use	Rangeland, forest, settlement, coast	-
	Presence of natural plants	Leafy forest, mixed forest, treeless area	Coniferous forest
	Average wind speed (m/s)	0-10	10-15
	Accommodation	Good	Medium
	Transport distance (m)	0-1000	1000 +
Agrotourism	Slope %	0-15	-
	Aspect	Flat, S, SE, SW	-
	Proximity to water sources (m)	0-500	500-1000
	Soil depth	Deep, Medium deep	-
	Land capability classes	I, II, III	IV
	Current land use	Cultivated agriculture, sown agriculture, hazelnut orchards	-
	Transport distance (m)	0-1000	1000 +

(Table 1 continues)

Figure 2. Flowchart of The Study

3. Findings

3.1. Suitability Analysis of Sustainable Tourism and Recreation Types for Kızılkum

Considering the natural and cultural values of the study area and taking into account the evaluation criteria for tourism activities determined based on expert opinions, spatial suitability analyzes were carried out through GIS. According to the results of the analysis, the tourism activity that covers the most area (34.47%) for the study area was determined as "Trekking/Nature Walking". As a result of the evaluations made, 41,130 km long recommended trekking and hiking routes were determined within the scope of the tourism activity" Scenic Viewing and Nature Photography", which stands out with a rate of 9.78%, and the hill points

on this route are important. The Güleadağı Hill (326 m) located in Büyükkızılkum Village, Tepedikharman Hill (300 m), Kıran Hill (225 m), Gürceağız Hill (141 m) near Kedi Kayası, and Mat Hill (137 m) in Küçükkızılkum Village represent the top five highest peak points, where the coastal, dune, forest, and rural settlement textures are most prominent. These areas, along with other lower-lying peak points, have been associated with trekking routes. In these points, tourism and recreational potential should be enhanced with the implementation of photography zones and observation terrace applications. Areas suitable for scenic viewing and nature photography, as well as trekking, in the study area are presented in Figure 3(a).

Agrotourism activity has been identified in the study area with a rate of 28.87%. Plants such as chestnut (*Castanea sativa*), hazelnut (*Corylus avellana*), wild strawberry (*Fragaria vesca*), and cornelian cherry (*Cornus mas*) found in Kızılkum are evaluated within the framework of agrotourism activities. It is of great importance to expand the research area within the agricultural pattern. The suitable areas identified for agrotourism in the study area are presented in Figure 3(b).

Flat and near-flat areas identified near the transportation routes between Büyükkızılkum, Hatipler, and predominantly Küçükkızılkum villages are defined as suitable areas for tent camping and picnicking. It has been determined that there are suitable areas for "16.91% picnic areas" and "16.01% tent camping areas" in the study area. Areas suitable for picnicking in the study area are presented in Figure 3(c), while areas suitable for tent camping are presented in Figure 3(d).

In addition to natural and cultural features, the research area is suitable for caravan camping with factors such as the absence of dense settlement texture, access to the sea and recognition of local culture. In the suitability analysis conducted, it has been observed that suitable areas for caravan camping, covering 17.51% of the area, are identified in large patches along the transportation routes between Büyükkızılkum, Hatipler, and predominantly Küçükkızılkum villages. Suitable areas for caravan camping in the study area are shown in Figure 3(e).

Other prominent tourism and recreational activities in the results are boating trips and swimming. In Kızılkum, which has a large and natural beach, suitable areas for "2.92% swimming" and "2.09% boating trips" are presented as a synthesis map in Figure 3(f).

Figure 2. Suitable Areas Identified for Tourism Types in The Study Area
The spatial and proportional distribution of tourism types in the study area is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Spatial and Proportional Distribution of Tourism Types in The Study Area

Tourism Activity	Area (km²)		%
Trekking	6,772	Length:41,130 (km)	%34,47
Agrotourism	5,672		%28,87
Caravan camping	3,441		%17,51
Picnic	3,323		%16,91
Tent camping	3,145		%16,01
Scenic viewing and nature photography	1,921		%9,78
Swimming	0,575		%2,92
Boating	0,410		%2,09

4. Discussion and Conclusion

Taking into account the natural and cultural values of the study area, the distribution of areas suitable for tourism and recreation activities was determined as a result of GIS analysis based on expert opinions. According to the findings, 34.47% of the study area was suitable for trekking, 28.87% for agrotourism, 16.91% for picnic, 16.01% for tent camping, 17.51% for caravan camping, 9.78% for scenic viewing and nature photography, 2.92% for swimming and 2.09% for boating.

It is an important strategy to realize the sale of natural species in the area to provide economic contribution at local and regional level. At the same time, wild strawberry (*Fragaria vesca*), which is an important agrotourism resource for the research area, should be emphasized in the branding process of Kızılkum region and should be evaluated by providing economic support. In terms of accessibility to Kızılkum, the improvement and expansion of road networks in the area, as well as the completion of infrastructure works, are strategically important to support tented camping and picnic activities.

Kızılkum, which has a wide and natural beach, is of great importance in terms of the sustainability of sea tourism and the completion of infrastructure works. Infrastructure improvements such as upgrading facilities for boat trips, including mooring places and pier connections, will significantly contribute to the feasibility and attractiveness of this activity in the region. In this context, organizing boat tours associated with nearby coves along the coastline can provide opportunities for integrated tourism and recreational activities.

Due to the current economic structure of Kızılkum, there is an observed tendency for the population to migrate. Evaluating the natural and cultural resources in the research area in terms of tourism and recreational potential can create a new economic support to prevent the population from decreasing every year. Considering the economic impacts of the social dimension of tourism, economically supporting and training local people in tourism activities is considered an effective strategy to promote tourism development in the region and reduce migration.

Within the scope of the research, when the natural and cultural resource values of Kızılkum and its immediate surroundings are considered in a holistic perspective, it is determined that the region has an important tourism and recreation potential. It is thought that this potential can contribute positively to local and regional development, and it is of great importance for the sustainable tourism and recreation development of Kızılkum, which is a priority area for protection, that this evaluation is carried out within the framework of holistic tourism planning and based on the principles of conservation and use.

Beritelli and Laesser (2017) define tourist destinations in recent years as a geographical area that needs to be organised, coordinated and made competitive in order for tourism to take place. The study advocates a shift from "one (fairly fixed) functional area" to "areas with multiple dynamic functions". Ronizi et al (2020) pointed out in his study that ecotourism activities can be carried out by giving importance to environmental protection. He stated that one of the important issues in this regard is the determination of a suitable location for ecotourism. The study presents an integrated approach to the development of ecotourism area.

As a result of the assessments conducted, it has been determined that Kızılkum has a high tourism and recreational potential. Suitability analyses have been conducted for activities such as scenic viewing, nature photography, tent camping, caravan camping, trekking, picnicking, swimming, boating trips, and agritourism. The research has emphasized that Kızılkum possesses prominent landscape features, which is an important factor in developing the potential of the region in terms of tourism and recreation. This article aims to provide a reference point for researchers, local managers and tourism professionals focusing on the sustainability of tourism in rural coastal areas.

It emphasizes that economic, environmental and social factors have a critical importance in the process of evaluating tourism potential and developing sustainable tourism practices in these regions. Cengiz et al (2021) and Cengiz et al (2022) contain similar evaluations in parallel with this study.

Furthermore, in the coastal regions of Kızılkum and Hatipler, there are ample picnic areas available for incoming tourists. Additionally, around Kızılkum and Hatipler Beach, there are flat and expansive areas offering camping facilities. Along the Black Sea shores of the study area, there are designated spots for professional and amateur fishermen to engage in angling. Moreover, in Kızılkum, motorized paragliding flights are conducted by the Western Black Sea Sports Aviation Club (BATIKAR). The paratrike aircraft provides an opportunity for tourists arriving throughout the summer season along the routes between Mugada and Kızılkum. In summary, the village of Kızılkum and its immediate surroundings serve as an ideal destination

for day trips or stays of a few days. Offering tourists various activities, including immersive nature experiences, sea-based activities, and thrilling sports opportunities.

References

- Aguilar-Becerra, C. D., Frausto-Martínez, O., Pineda, H. A. and Acevedo, J. L. R. (2017). Use of Sustainable Tourism Indicators for Rural Coastal Communities: A Review. *WIT Transactions on Ecology and the Environment*, 226, 803-814.
- Aref, F. and Gill, S. S. (2009). Rural Tourism Development Through Rural Cooperatives. *Nature and Science*, 7(10), 68-73.
- Ayhan, Ç. K., Taşlı, T. C., Özkök, F. and Tatlı, H. (2020). Land Use Suitability Analysis of Rural Tourism Activities: Yenice, Turkey. *Tourism Management*, 76, 103949.
- Benliay, A. (2009). Peyzaj Planı Oluşturulması Bağlamında Finike-Kumluca Kıyı Bölgesinin Değerlendirilmesi. Doktora Tezi, Ankara Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Ankara, 235 s.
- Beritelli, P. and Laesser, C. (2017). The Dynamics of Destinations and Tourism Development. *Design Science in Tourism: Foundations of Destination Management*, 195-214, Springer, Berlin, Germany.
- Castellani, V. and Sala, S. (2010). Sustainable Performance Index for Tourism Policy development. *Tourism Management*, 31(6), 871-880.
- Cengiz, C., Sahin, Ş., Cengiz, B., Başkır, M.B. and Keçecioglu Dağlı, P. (2021). Evaluation of The Visitor Understanding of Coastal Geotourism and Geoheritage Potential Based On Sustainable Regional Development in Western Black Sea Region, Turkey. *Sustainability*, 13(21), 11812.
- Cengiz, C., Cengiz, B., Smardon, R.C. (2022). A Bridge between Coastal Resilience and Tourism-Recreation: Multifunctional Benefit of Boardwalk Design for Sustainable Development in the Western Black Sea Region, Turkey. *Water*, 14(9), 1434.
- Doğaner, Y. (1996). Tarımsal Taslak Sektör Raporu. Patara Özel Çevre Koruma Bölgesi Yönetim Planı Bilimsel Araştırmaları Sektör Raporu. Çevre Bakanlığı Özel Çevre Koruma Kurumu Başkanlığı ve Kültür Bakanlığı Kültür ve Tabiat Varlıkları Koruma Genel Müdürlüğü Yayınları, Ankara.
- Ergör, B. (1984). Dağcılık Tekniği. *Dağcılık Federasyonu Yayınları*. Ankara.
- Fan, H. (2020). Research on Sustainable Development of Coastal Rural Ecotourism Based on Tourism Perception. *Journal of Coastal Research*, 115(SI), 53-55.
- Fithor, A., Prayitno, S. B., Purwanti, F. and Indarjo, A. (2020). Tourism Suitability, and Carrying Capacity: Prospect Ecotourism (Case Study in Marina Beach Semarang). In *E3S Web of Conferences 202*, EDP Sciences.
- Gıran Taşcıoğlu, S. (2016). Sürdürülebilir Turizm İçin Stratejilerin Geliştirilmesi: Kuzey Antalya Kültür ve Turizm Koruma ve Gelişim Bölgesi Örneği. Doktora Tezi, Ankara Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Ankara, 413 s.
- Havur, M. (2002). Sözlü Görüşme. Ankara Rehberler Derneği. Maltepe. Ankara
- Jayaraman, R., Kumar, B.S. and Singh, S.K. (2021). Remote Sensing and Gis Based Site Suitability Analysis For Tourism Development in Vaishali Block, Bihar, India. *Acta*

Geographica Debrecina Landscape & Environment, 15(2), 12-22.

- Kiper, T. (2006). Safranbolu Yörükköyü Peyzaj Potansiyelinin Kırsal Turizm Açısından Değerlendirilmesi. Doktora Tezi, Ankara Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Ankara, 367 s.
- Lantitsou, K. (2017). Eco-Development and Environmental Spatial Planning. *Fresenius Environmental Bulletin, 26(2)*, 1291-1300.
- Li, J., (2020). Research on The Development Of Coastal Rural Tourism in China from The Perspective of Industrial Integration. in: Bai, X. and Zhou, H. (eds.), *Advances in Water Resources, Environmental Protection, and Sustainable Development. Journal of Coastal Research, 115*, 271-273. Coconut Creek (Florida), ISSN 0749-0208.
- Mazahreh, S., Bsoul, M. and Hamoor, D. A. (2019). GIS Approach for Assessment of Land Suitability for Different Land Use Alternatives in Semi Arid Environment in Jordan: Case Study (Al Gadeer Alabyad-Mafraq). *Information Processing in Agriculture, 6(1)*, 91-108.
- Miller, M. L., Auyong, J. and Hadley, N. P. (2002). Sustainable Coastal Tourism: Challenges for Management, Planning, And Education. Retrieved March, 10, 2017.
- Norouzi, A. and Moradi, N. (2019). Eastern Regions of Isfahan Province. *Journal of Research and Rural Planning, 8(2)*, 77-96.
- Okyar, T., Okay, H. and Tapan, H. (1991). İstatistik yıllığı 1984-1989. *Tarım ve Köy İşleri Bakanlığı Köy Hizmetleri Genel Müdürlüğü Araştırma Planlama ve Koordinasyon Dairesi Başkanlığı Yayınları*, Ankara.
- Rogerson, C. M. and Rogerson, J. M. (2020). Coastal Tourism in South Africa: A Geographical Perspective. *New Directions in South African Tourism Geographies, 227-247*.
- Ronizi, S. R. A., Mokarram, M. and Negahban, S. (2020). Utilizing Multi-Criteria Decision to Determine The Best Location for The Ecotourism in The East and Central of Fars Province, Iran. *Land Use Policy, 99*, 105095, Land Use Policy.
- Sharpley, R. (2002). Rural Tourism and The Challenge of Tourism Diversification: The Case of Cyprus. *Tourism management, 23(3)*, 233-244.
- Šiljeg, A., Cavrić, B., Šiljeg, S., Marić, I. and Barada, M. (2019). Land suitability zoning for ecotourism planning and development of Dikgatlhong Dam, Botswana. *Geographica Pannonica, 23(2)*, 76-86.
- Sözen, N. ve Şahin, Ş. 1998. Kamping (Planlama–Uygulama–İşletme), Peyzaj Mimarisi Derneği Yayınları. 1998/1. Ankara.
- Stoddart, M. C., Catano, G., Ramos, H., Vodden, K., Lowery, B. and Butters, L. (2020). Collaboration gaps and regional tourism networks in rural coastal communities. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism, 28(4)*, 625-645.
- Susila, I., Dean, D., Harismah, K., Priyono, K. D., Setyawan, A. A. and Maulana, H. (2023). Does Interconnectivity Matter? An Integration Model of Agro-Tourism Development. *Asia Pacific Management Review*.
- Tawfık, R. and Elsebaei, M. (2022). Assessing The Rural Lodges and Stakeholders'perceptions for Agritourism. *Fresenius Environmental Bulletin, 31(11)*, 10663-10673.
- Topay, M. (2003). Bartın-Uluyayla Peyzaj Özelliklerinin Rekreasyon-Turizm Kullanımları Açısından Değerlendirilmesi Üzerine Bir Araştırma. Doktora Tezi, Ankara Üniversitesi

Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Ankara, 210 s.

Utami, D. D., Dhewanto, W. and Lestari, Y. D. (2023). Rural Tourism Entrepreneurship Success Factors for Sustainable Tourism Village: Evidence from Indonesia. *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(1), 2180845.

Ethics Committee Permission

Since the research data was collected in 2018, ethics committee approval was not required.

Contribution Rate Declaration

1. Author: %60,

2. Author: %40

Sponsor Statement

This article is derived from the Master's thesis completed at Bartın University, Institute of Science, Department of Landscape Architecture. The thesis study was supported by the Bartın University Scientific Research Projects titled “Bartın-Kızılıkum Kırsal Kıyı Yerleşiminin Sürdürülebilir Turizm ve Rekreasyon Potansiyeli Yönünden Değerlendirilmesi” with the code 2018-FEN-CY-007 and I would like to thank Bartın University.

